

Analysis of Strategic Planning of Educational Tourism Based on Local Wisdom in Indonesia

Ari Putra¹, Dr. H. Mustofa Kamil²

¹Departement of Community Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung, West Java, Indonesia.

²Jl. Dr. Setiabudhi No 229, Isola, Sukasari, Kota Bandung

Corresponding Author: Ari Putra

ABSTRACT

This study was departed from the importance in improving the quality of educators and education staff from various aspects of educational ways which exist in Indonesia. Strategic planning is carried out by each institution in order to formulate the plans that will be carried out by the institution both in the long term or short term. This study aims to determine the strategic plan of the *ECO Bambu Cipaku* institution in improving the quality of educators and education staff. The end of this study is to formulate a strategy for education in terms of preparing educators and education to improve competitiveness with other educational tours. This research using a qualitative method and the analysis of the data which was used is the *S.W.O.T* (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis. The results of this study indicate that the *ECO Bambu Cipaku* which is known as an educational tourism institution is in a very good position. Its position is in the range of values of 0.7 and in the quadrant I of aggressive strategy where the institution utilizes various internal strengths so that it can draw on external opportunities.

Keywords: Strategic planing, educational tourism, local wisdom.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current development requires every individual to be ready with any kind of challenges given. Furthermore, the development of this era requires every individual to be qualified so that they are able to compete in order to improve the human development. Furthermore; every individual is required to have several additional skills in facing the global competition. The high demanding of competition in education field causes the educational institutions to prepare, carry out organizational transformation, seek their excellence that can ensure their existence in the middle of high competition (Edi Suandi Hamid, 2008:2). Thus, the improvement can be applied in to some education and training activities, seminars and workshops.

The large number of educational institutions in Indonesia has created some competition to attract learners to join the learning process at those educational institutions. Lifelong Learning is a concept where there is a correlation between learning and behavior that comes from individual experiences. (Michael Strain, 1998:264). In Act No 20 year 2003 explained that education in Indonesia have three lines civic, ranging from formal education, non-formal education, and informal education. With the presence of the three institutions is expected to increase the potential of human resources in Indonesia starting from the realm of cognitive, affective and psychomotor. One direction of the long-term development of this human resources kualias human resources

enhancement is implemented through increased access and equity, quality and relevance, as well as the management of social services/base, which include health, nutrition, education, family planning and social welfare; the improvement of the quality of the workforce; improved quality of life and the unity of life and religious intern; and social protection.

Quality education is education which is able to realize the expectations of society, developing the potential of each individual being's ability to meet all the necessities of life and the demands of the times. The quality of a country's education becomes a barometer of the degree of progress which positioned the country's dignity in the world.

One of the factors determining the quality of education is the quality of human resources within the scope of the institution better known as quality educators and educational personnel. According to law No. 20 years 2013 Article 39 para 1 and 2 put forth that the Educator is a professional personnel in charge of planning and implementing the process of learning, assessing learning outcomes, conduct supervision and training, as well as do your research and dedication to the community, especially for educators at the College. While the educational personnel in charge of administration, management, development, supervision, and technical services to support the educational process in educational units. Educational institutions have ample opportunity to improve the quality of produce educators and educators that are within the scope of the educational unit. This is because each agency has an obligation to improve the quality of education in the unit include improved quality of educators and educational personnel. On the institution of pendidikan non-formal educators are obliged to: (a) create a meaningful education, fun, creative, and dialogis; (b) has the commitment to professionally untukmeningkatkan quality of education; and (c) give the example and

keep the good name of the institution, profession, and position in accordance with the trust given to him (Djuju Sudjana, 2006:16). The quality of education is a degree of excellence in management education effectively and efficiently to deliver academic excellence and extracurricular on learners who declared for one level of education or completing the learner certain Ness (Marus Suti, 2011:2).

Educators-formal education consists of teachers ' learning, tutor, instructor, and early childhood Education teachers. As for the power of education is in charge of personnel administration, management, development, supervision, and technical services for the menunjang proses education in the education unit. These consist of produce educator's overseer, the Organizer/Manager educational unit, librarian, and professional organization of educators and non-formal education educational staff (PTK-PNF) (Djuju Sudjana, 2006:16).

ECO Bambu Cipaku is a non-formal educational institution which organizes educational alternative in the form of educational tours. Significantly, the learning experience can be found in the educational tour because it is considered covers a few things ranging from actual experience and the preparation of learners (Pitman Et all, 2010:234). Quality improvement facilitator is one form of bersaingnya institution. Quality educator development can improve the quality of the output which is studied at the Institute as well as the competitive power. In addition, the increase in competitiveness is done by applying the right strategies through analysis of internal and external factors on the facilitator and Manager at *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung. The purpose of this research was: analyzing the problems that occur on the system quality improvement facilitator and Manager at *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung devise strategies in an attempt to increase the competitiveness of the facilitator and Manager at *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung

through S.W.O.T analysis, 4) Determine the appropriate strategy to increase the facilitator and Manager at *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative method which was allowed the researchers to think through inductive way. This study also can be categorized as a case study since the research problems discussed in this study originally raised at *ECO Bambu Cipaku*. The researcher described the data by explaining and analyzing the strategic plan of community education institutions on developing the quality of facilitators and educational tourism education staff that were owned by *ECO Bambu Cipaku*. In collecting the data, this study used techniques: participation observation and open and in-depth interviews. In analyzing the data, this study employed S.W.O.T technique with qualitative approach which are consisted of “Strengths”, “Weaknesses”, “Opportunities” and “Threats”. According to Fredi Rangkuti (2004:18) S.W.O.T analysis is known as systematic identification of various factors to formulate the company's strategy. Furthermore, S.W.O.T analysis aims to maximize the “strength” and “opportunities”. However, it also can minimize the “weakness” and “threats”. It is relevant with Porter's statement (2007:71) who stated that the implementation of the strategy deals with three approaches: 1) overall cost advantage, 2) differentiation, and 3) focus.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

ECO Bambu Cipaku is included in the units of the non formal education programmes in the concept of leisure education program specialties. Recreation education is a concept of education which provides learning opportunities for students to find out a few things in accordance with the tourism education programs provided. Educational tour is divided into several

programs. The one of the program is the introduction of culture and citizenship.

ECO Bambu Cipaku as a community education institution was established with the aim of introducing the cultures that exist in the West Java province. With the presence of this institution, it can provide character strengthening for learners, because the institution's main mission is local wisdom-based character education. The findings of this study are in the form of the results of an analysis of the quality standards of educators and educational staff.

This educational institution always provides learning to try to provide the best educational services to the community. This is evidenced by the educational qualifications in this institution. Facilitators owned by this institution already have bachelor education standards. In order to improve facilitators from this institution, there is ongoing training for facilitators. The number of educators owned by *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is 15 persons and 3 of them are educational staff. The managers in this educational institution have a doctoral level degree qualification. When viewed from the composition of educational background, this institution already has very classy educational standards. To increase competitiveness, in addition to facilitators who already have undergraduate education qualifications, education managers have a doctoral education background. it can be concluded that it has fulfilled the qualifications as determined by the standards of educators and education personnel determined by the government

The analysis of the determinants of the success of this institutional, one of which can be seen from cultural organizations that applied to surroundings of the institution. In addition, these educational institutions have volunteers as a complement to the education component in order to meet the needs of learners. They come from the University partner institutions and from community group. The Manager in this case has the educational

background of Doctoral Education, a much contribute towards the advancement of institution, where the manager can be a professional leader and managerial the institution can be effectively.

The various problems faced by the institutional, among others are the problems associated with the large number of educational tours move with the mission of introducing local culture that does not survive. That's models of learning at educational tourism have no interested for learner and join to learn. This problem is caused by the incessant promotion of less institutional. If the local culture can be seen the appeal of his own with the uniqueness of the learning offer. Another problem is infrastructure. Infrastructure is still in the fulfillment stage such as internet access, building renovation and classrooms as well as traditional game kit training and reading collections.

A. Internal Factors Analysis

Internal factor analysis is an activity carried out with the aim of finding an overview of conditions that affect the development and quality of facilitators of *ECO Bambu Cipaku*. *S.W.O.T* analysis techniques can be used as a way to look at strategic plans and ultimately make them flexible instruments (Betsy Orr, 2013: 382). In addition, this analysis is also carried out to examine various factors that can be "strengths", "weaknesses", "opportunities" and "threats" of the facilitator and educational staff in *ECO Bambu Cipaku*.

1) Analysis of Strengths Internal Factors.

The strength possessed by this institution is that the facilitator has qualified bachelor of education and has taken basic training in traditional games by local cultural education tourism institutions or organizations. The educational background of the education facilitator is in accordance with the knowledge that the institution should have, namely community education. Managers owned by this institution already have an educational qualification, namely a Doctor

in the field of education in this case the figure who is the starting point in the progress of the institution. The institution has a maintainer who already have qualified Doctoral Education with educational qualifications so that is owned by the person who manages the *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung are expected to managing the institutions can be effectively and efficiently in accordance with the conditions to be expected by users of the service of education.

2) Analysis of Weakness Internal Factors.

Based on the results of the internal factor analysis on the standards of produce educators and facilitators in *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung city, it can be deduced some things become weakness associated with the quality the quality of produce educators and facilitators in *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung. The task of the facilitator is to develop scientific knowledge by developing his profession in a sustainable manner both in terms of 1). Self-development, which includes: a) the following education and training both at the elementary, secondary and even levels. In addition to attending education and training, facilitators must take part in several activities that can support the training followed, such as scientific activities, seminars related to the development of scientific knowledge, exploration and experimentation on traditional games that can be introduced to learning activities in educational tourism; and broadening one's ability to learn and follow the development of standard service components such as making technical guidance on activities. Facilitators are individuals who are able to conceptualize learning in the form of learning tools / components. However, in its implementation, the facilitator was still unable to make learning and teaching material. The low ability of a facilitator in creating a learning component is certainly one of the limiting factors for the success of facilitators in improving quality.

B. Analysis of Opportunity and threats External Factor

Based on the results of the analysis of external factors on the quality of facilitators and education staff, several things can be formulated that can be categorized in terms of opportunities and threats from facilitators and education staff in this educational tourism institution.

1) The analysis of external factors opportunity

The opportunities that can be utilized by *ECO Bambu Cipaku* which is located in Bandung in order to improve the quality of facilitators and education staff are as follows:

- a. The local government policy towards the implementation of regional education curriculum that is called as Bandung *Masagi* Curriculum was integrated with formal, non-formal and informal education.
- b. Having opportunities to join the tiered training ranging from basic, intermediate to advanced which is aimed to improve the quality of the trainers.
- c. The availability of speech retrieval activities, focus group discussion, and proper seminars that is held by Government, universities, and related institutions for the science development.

2) The analysis of external threats factors.

- a. Lack of interest to take part in learning in several places that has cultural education base.
- b. The high competitiveness of educational tours with a more modern educational tourist model
- c. The high expectations of the facilitators as a professional who is always reliable in everything.

C. IFAS and EFAS Matrix

Internal Factor Analysis Strategy (IFAS) and External Factor Analysis Strategy (EFAS) matrices are known as a matrix that contains internal and external environmental analysis factors by including weighting, rating and scores (the result of multiplication between weighting and rating) in each factor analysis.

1) IFAS Matrix

Based on the analysis of the internal environment through an analysis of strengths and weaknesses in *ECO Bambu Cipaku*, the result was related to the standard of the facilitator. Therefore, the IFAS matrix of *ECO Bambu Cipaku* can be formulated as follows.

Tabel 1 Internal Factor Analysis Strategy (IFAS)

Analysis of internal starategy factor	Intergrity	Rating	Score
Strength			
a. Facilitators <i>ECO Bambu Cipaku</i> Bandung have qualified as Bachelor degree.	0,25	3	0,75
b. Facilitators <i>ECO Bambu Cipaku</i> Bandung city have participated the activities that related with the facilitators' quality through tiered training.	0,23	3	0,69
c. The Manager/CEO of <i>ECO Bambu Cipaku</i> Bandung is qualified as Doctoral Education in science education.	0,17	3	0,51
Total	0,65	11	1,95
Weakness:			
a. The number of facilitators in <i>ECO Bambu Cipaku</i> Bandung which is active in implementing the sustainable development of professionalism only 8%.	0,20	4	0,8
b. The Facilitators who are able to create a learning component are less than 50%	0,15	3	0,45
Score	0,37	5	1,25
Total	1	15	3,2

2) EFAS Matrix

Based on the data analysis of external environment which focused on the opportunities and threats contained in *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is related to the standard of the facilitator. It can be formulated as follows.:

Tabel 2 External Factor Analysis Strategy (EFAS)

External factor analysis strategy	Bobot	Peringkat	Skor
Opportunity			
a. Government policy areas on the implementation of educational curriculum (Bandung Masagi Curriculum).	0,23	4	0,92
b. The availability of opportunities to join tiered training regarding to the improvement of trainers' quality.	0,20	3	0,6
c. Large number of workshops and seminar from Government, Universities and professional organizations for the development of science.	0,12	3	0,36
Jumlah	0,55	10	1,88
Ancaman			
a. Lack of interest to take part in learning in several places that has cultural education base.	0,10	2	0,2
b. The high competitiveness of educational tours with a more modern educational tourist model	0,20	2	0,4
c. The high expectations of the facilitators as a professional who is always reliable in everything.	0,15	3	0,45
	0,45	5	1,05
Total	1	15	2,93

D. The Position of ECO Bambu Cipaku based on IFAS and EFAS Matrix

Based on the calculation results towards IFAS and EFAS matrix above, it can be concluded that:

1. Total Strength Score owned *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is 1.95
2. Total weakness Score owned *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is 1.25
3. Total opportunities Score that can be exploited by *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung was 1.88
4. Total threats Score that faced by *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is 1.05

The brief explanation about each total score of IFAS and EFAS matrix of *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung can be seen in the following table.

Tabel 3 Total Score Matrik IFAS DAN EFAS

Analysis Factors	Total
Strenght	1,95
Weakness	1,25
Opportunities	1,88
Threats	1,05

According to the table 3, the calculation based on matrix of IFAD and EFAS is obtained, it can be concluded that *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung City in the aspect of educators and education staff has a greater strength than weakness and has a greater opportunity than the threat.

To be able to determine the strategic position of *ECO Bambu Cipaku* in Bandung City in terms of the standard aspects of

facilitators and educational staff on a diagram, it was consisted of 4 quadrants, then determined in advance the X-and Y - coordinate. X coordinate consists of the factors the internal environment is the reduction the weighting score of strengths and weaknesses. (Coordinate X = weighted score Power – the weighting score Weakness). While the Y coordinate consists of external environmental factors which is a reduction in weight of score from the opportunities and threats (coordinate Y = weighted score Opportunities – the weighting score Threat). Based on the above, it can be noted that.

1. Coordinate X
Coordinate X = Score Strength – Score Weakness = 1,95 – 1,25 = 0,7
2. Coordinate Y
Coordinate Y = Score Opportunities – Score Threats = 1,88 – 1,05 = 0,83

Based on the analayis above, it can be known that *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is located in quadrant I (Strategy Aggressive). It showed that *ECO Bambu Cipaku* Bandung is located in a very good situation because there are forces that are utilized to achieve a profitable opportunity. With positions like this then the aspects of standards facilitator and Manager positions ready to flourish. For more detail explanation about the strategic positions of Bandung Cipaku Bambu ECO, it can be seen in the following chart.

Gambar 1. Strategic Positions of ECO Bambu Cipaku in Aspect Standard of Facilitator and Educational Staff.

4. CONCLUSION

The conclusions of the study that focused on the analysis of facilitators' quality of facilitator and educational staff in *ECO Bambu Cipaku* are in aggressive strategy positions, where the institution can position itself to get the opportunity to take advantage of its opportunities. The strategy used as the institution's priority point is to conduct training activities carried out by institutions and other educational institutions to improve the ability of facilitators to face competition.

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